

NOTES

Hibiscetin Heptamethyl Ether, a Natural Flavone*

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In continuation of our studies¹ of *Murraya exotica* from taxonomic considerations, we report our further work on the heterocyclic constituents of this plant. Since our report on mexoticin (I), C₁₆H₂₀O₆ [α]_D+37.6°, (CHCl₃) m.p. 185°, two coumarins, coumarrayin^{2,3} (II), and alosin⁴ and two flavonoids (III) and (IV) have been reported from this plant.

Dreyer³ isolated coumarrayin (II) and a flavonoid (III) isolated previously from the fruits of *M. exotica* and was synthesised by Jefferies *et al.*⁵, Joshi *et al.*⁶ on the other hand reported exoticin (IV) from the leaves of the plant and could not obtain the flavonoid reported by Dreyer. The absence of the flavonoid (III) and the closely related compounds in their isolates has been attributed by Joshi *et al.* to geographical and ecological factors. Dreyer³ on the other hand could not however attribute the absence of mexoticin in his isolates to a particular reason. He concluded that the discrepancy might be due to climatic, seasonal, geographical and genetic differences in the plant materials.

In the present communication, we report some of the results of our investigations with different parts of the plant. The report on hibiscetin heptamethyl ether (V), hitherto unknown in plant kingdom, forms the major part of the present communication.

From the fruits of *Murraya exotica* we have isolated two flavonoids. One of them, m.p. 155–56° (M⁺ 432) showed N.M.R. and mass spectral data identical with the compound (III) previously reported³. The identity was confirmed by comparison with an authentic specimen of the sample kindly supplied by Prof. Dreyer.

* Part XXV in the series Chemical Taxonomy. Part XXIV, D. P. Chakraborty, S. P. Basak, B. C. Das and R. Beugelmans, *Phytochemistry*, 1970 (in press).

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16 hr. The benzene extract, on removal of the solvent, yielded a brown semisolid mass which was dissolved in ether and separated into acidic, basic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over alumina. First four fractions (50 ml. each) eluted from the column with benzene gave, on removal of the solvent, a solid residue m.p. 151–52°. The compound on crystallisation from methanol afforded (III) as colourless crystals, m.p. 156°. This was identified with a sample of (III) provided by Prof. Dryer (m.m.p., t.l.c., i.r.).

From 5th to 8th fractions (50 ml each) eluted with benzene a light yellow solid, m.p. 191–93° was obtained after removal of the solvent. The solid on crystallisation from methanol furnished hibiscetin heptamethyl ether (identified as follows) m.p. 196–97° in light yellow crystals (yield 50 mg)⁹.

Preparation of (V) from (VII): Compound (VII) was dissolved in methanol and to it was added an ethereal solution of diazomethane. On working up as usual, an alkali insoluble compound crystallisable from alcohol, m.p. 196° was obtained. This was identical with the compound V (m.m.p., t.l.c.).

Isolation of coumarrayin (II): The dried and powdered root bark of *Murraya exotica* (600 g) was extracted in a soxhlet with benzene for 18 hr. The extract, after removal of the solvent, was taken up in ether and separated into acidic, basic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over alumina and from the first ten fractions (50 ml each) eluted from the column with benzene, a colourless crystalline compound, m.p. 150–52° was obtained. The compound on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether mixture afforded a compound, m.p. 157° which was found to be identical with coumarrayin (II), by m.m.p., t.l.c. and superimposable i.r. spectra (yield 400 mg.).

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9. There was paucity of material, the compound was homogeneous by mass spectrometry and t.l.c. and identical with synthetic specimen. No analysis for C, H was carried out.